

THE COURSE OF FETOPLACENTAL INSUFFICIENCY, SEVERITY AND SPECIFICITY OF TREATMENT

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Fetoplacental insufficiency (FPI) is one of the major problems in the field of obstetrics today. 'lum emas. Fetoplacental insufficiency (FPI) is now a set of symptoms caused by various disorders of the placenta and fetus due to various diseases and obstetric complications. The different variants of FPI manifestation, the frequency and severity of complications for the pregnant woman and the fetus, the predominance of a particular placental function depend on the duration of pregnancy, the strength, duration and nature of the effect. detrimental factors, as well as the severity of the compensatory-adaptive capacity of the mother-placenta-fetal system during the developmental stage of the fetus and placenta.

Classification of FPI: The compensated form of FPI is characterized by the initial manifestations of the pathological process in the fetoplacental complex. Protective and adaptive mechanisms are activated and experience a certain tension, which creates conditions for the further development of the fetus and the development of the fetus. With adequate therapy and birth control, a healthy baby can be born. The subcompensated form is characterized by an increase in the severity of the complication. In the decompensated form, overexertion and disruption of compensatory-adaptive mechanisms occur, which do not provide the necessary conditions for the subsequent normal development of pregnancy.

Diagnosis of FPI: Dopplerography is a very informative, relatively simple and safe diagnostic method that can be used for comprehensive dynamic monitoring of the state of blood circulation in the mother-placenta-fetal system after 18-19 weeks of gestation, because by this time the second stage of pregnancy lqini begins. cytotrophoblast invasion is complete. The nature of hemodynamics in the umbilical arteries makes it possible to assess the state of fetoplacental blood flow and microcirculation in the fetal part of the placenta. Studies of the uterine arteries on both sides are performed to diagnose uteroplacental blood flow disorders

An important component of a comprehensive assessment of fetal status is cardiotocography (CTG), a method of functional assessment of fetal status based on recording its heart rate and changes in their uterine contractions, exposure to external stimuli, or their changes. the activity of the fetus itself. CTG significantly expands the possibilities of antenatal diagnosis, allowing you to address the issues of rational tactics of pregnancy management. Treatment of pregnant women with FPY

Treatment of FPY should be aimed at improving uteroplacental and fetoplacental blood flow; increased gas exchange; correction of rheological and coagulation properties of blood; elimination of hypovolemia and hypoproteinemia; normalization of vascular tone and contractile activity of the uterus; enhanced antioxidant protection; optimization of metabolic and metabolic processes. Due to the individual combination of etiological factors and pathogenetic mechanisms for the development of this complication, a standard scheme of treatment of FPI may not be available. The choice of drugs should be made individually in each specific observation and should be differentiated taking into account the severity and duration of the complication, etiological factors and pathogenetic mechanisms based on this pathology. Dosage and duration of use of drugs require an individual approach. Attention should be paid to correcting the side effects of some medications.

The need for magnesium during pregnancy increases by 2-3 times due to the growth and development of the fetus and placenta. Magnesium, which is involved in more than 300 enzymatic reactions, is necessary for fetal growth. Magnesium ions are involved in the synthesis of DNA and RNA. Successfully combining magnesium with pyridoxine, it is a cation of more than 50 enzymatic reactions that ensures protein metabolism, participates in the synthesis and absorption of amino acids, promotes the formation of hemoglobin in erythrocytes, which is especially important for the growing embryo and fetus . Therefore, in the presence of placental insufficiency and fetal malnutrition, the use of magnesium supplements is most preferable.

Magnesium (Magne B6® forte) has a positive effect on uteroplacental circulation, so its appointment is indicated for the treatment of placental insufficiency and fetal malnutrition. A parallel was established between the magnesium concentrations in the blood serum, myometrium, and placenta. Magne B6® forte also goes well with angioprotectants, angioactive agents (Trental, Curantil, Mildronate, Actovegin, etc.), antioxidants - vitamins E, C, B group and others.

If FPY is detected, it is recommended that the pregnant woman be hospitalized for in-depth examination and treatment. Pregnant women with a compensated form of FPY may be excluded if initiated treatment has a positive

effect and the necessary conditions for dynamic clinical and instrumental monitoring of the nature of pregnancy and the effectiveness of therapy are available. A leading role in the implementation of therapeutic measures is the treatment of the underlying disease or complication in which FPY occurs. At present, unfortunately, it is not possible to completely rid a pregnant woman of FPY with any therapeutic effect. Applied therapies only help to stabilize the existing pathological process and maintain compensatory-adaptive mechanisms to the extent that the optimal optimal duration of pregnancy lasts until birth.

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